

NOTES ON THE ORDER OF CONVERGENCE, CONSISTENCY AND STABILITY PROPERTIES OF NEWLY DERIVED SCHEMES

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Abstract: *In this paper, two numerical integration methods for solving Initial Value Problems (IVPs) in Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs), namely “Third Order One Step Scheme (TOOSS) and Second Order One Step Scheme (SOOSS)” have been considered. The order of convergence, consistency and the stability properties of the schemes have been investigated. From the analyses, it is observed that SOOSS and TOOSS have second order convergence and third order convergence, respectively. It is also observed that both numerical integration methods are consistent and stable. Moreover, three IVPs of stiff differential equations were solved to examine the performance of SOOSS and TOOSS in terms of absolute relative errors. Hence, the numerical results show that TOOSS performs better than SOOSS because of its higher order of accuracy.*

Keywords: *Accuracy, consistency, convergence, final absolute relative error, stability region, stiff differential equation.*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematical model is a means of translating real life situations into mathematical symbols and relations. This concept is commonly used in Sciences and Engineering. Models are developed to help in understanding of physical phenomena. These models frequently resulted in equations that contain derivatives of unknown function of one or several variables. These types of equations are referred to as Differential Equations. Differential equations are not only encountered in physical sciences, but also in diverse fields like Economics, Medicine, Psychology, Operation Research and even in areas such as Biology and Anthropology. In reality, the analytical solutions of some of the equations arising from modelling of real life situations might not be easily obtained.

This necessitated the need for approximate solution by the application of numerical methods. To that extent, several algorithms have been proposed in literature based on the nature and the type of the differential equations to be solved such as Wambecq (1976), Jain (2003), Davis (2013), Qureshi et al. (2013), Fadugba and Falodun (2017), Fadugba and Okunlola (2017), just to mention a few. This paper is motivated by the work of Qureshi and Fadugba (2018). In this paper, the order of convergence,

consistency and stability properties of the FadugbaFalodun and Fadugba-Okunlola schemes were investigated. The TOOSS and SOOSS have been applied on IVPs of first and second order ODEs (Fadugba and Ajayi, 2017; Qureshi and Fadugba, 2018; Fadugba, 2019; Fadugba, 2020). Therefore, Equation 4 becomes: $LTE(TOOSS) \approx y(x_n) + hf(x_n, y(x_n)) + \frac{1}{2}h^2 f^{(1)}(x_n, y(x_n))$

ORDER OF CONVERGENCE OF THE SCHEMES $\frac{1}{3} f^{(2)}(x_n, y(x_n)) + \frac{h^2}{2} f^{(1)}(x_n, y(x_n)) + \frac{1}{4} f^{(3)}(x_n, y(x_n)) + O(h^5)$

In order to check the order of convergence of the schemes, the formula of the schemes is subtracted from the Taylor's series expansion for $y(x)$ in powers of h under the localizing assumptions. The convergence of TOOSS and SOOSS is presented as follows.

$$y(x_n + h) = y(x_n) + hf(x, y) + \frac{1}{2}h^2 f^{(1)}(x, y) + \frac{1}{6}h^3 f^{(2)}(x, y) + \frac{1}{24}h^4 f^{(3)}(x, y) + \dots$$

$$y(x_n + h) - y(x_n) = hf(x, y) + \frac{1}{2}h^2 f^{(1)}(x, y) + \frac{1}{6}h^3 f^{(2)}(x, y) + \frac{1}{24}h^4 f^{(3)}(x, y) + \dots$$

Thus,

Order of convergence of TOOSS

$$LTE(TOOSS) \approx y(x_n) + hf(x_n, y(x_n)) + \frac{1}{2}h^2 f^{(1)}(x_n, y(x_n))$$

From the Taylor's series, one obtains:

$$\frac{1}{3!}hf(x_n, y(x_n)) + \frac{1}{4!}hf(x_n, y(x_n)) + O(h)$$

$$y(x_n + h) - y(x_n) = hf(x_n, y(x_n)) + \frac{1}{2}h^2 f^{(1)}(x_n, y(x_n)) + \frac{1}{6}h^3 f^{(2)}(x_n, y(x_n)) + \frac{1}{24}h^4 f^{(3)}(x_n, y(x_n)) + \dots$$

$$\frac{1}{3!}hf(x_n, y(x_n)) + \frac{1}{4!}hf(x_n, y(x_n)) + O(h)$$

$$y(x_n) + hf(x_n, y(x_n)) + \frac{1}{2}h^2 f^{(1)}(x_n, y(x_n)) + \frac{1}{6}h^3 f^{(2)}(x_n, y(x_n)) + \frac{1}{24}h^4 f^{(3)}(x_n, y(x_n)) + \dots$$

$$\frac{1}{3!}hf(x_n, y(x_n)) + \frac{1}{4!}hf(x_n, y(x_n)) + O(h)$$

(1)

Fadugba and Okunlola (2017) derived a scheme of the form:

$$y_{n+1} - y_n = h \left[(2h - 1) f^{(2)}(x_n, y_n) + h^2 f^{(3)}(x_n, y_n) + 14 f^{(2)}(x_n, y_n) \right] \quad (1)$$

$$- \left[h^2 f^{(1)}(x_n, y_n) + 1 f^{(2)}(x_n, y_n) \right] \quad (2)$$

$$2 \left[-2 \right] \quad (2)$$

Using Equations 1 and 2, the local truncation error becomes:

$$LTE(TOOSS) = y(x_{n+1} - h) - y_{n+1} \quad (3)$$

(3)

$$1 - 2 f^{(1)}(x_n, y(x_n)) LTE(TOOSS) = y(x_n) - h f(x_n, y(x_n)) - h^2$$

$$1 - 3 f^{(2)}(x_n, y(x_n)) - 1 h^4 f^{(3)}(x_n, y(x_n)) - O(h^5)$$

$$- h$$

$$3! - 4!$$

$$- y_n - 1 (2h - 1) f^{(2)}(x_n, y_n) - h^2 f^{(3)}(x_n, y_n) - 1 f^{(2)}(x_n, y_n) \quad (4)$$

8

$$4$$

$$h^2 f^{(1)}(x_n, y_n) + 1 f^{(2)}(x_n, y_n) \quad (4)$$

$$2 - 2$$

(4)

Replacing the term e^{2h} in Equation 4 by its Maclaurin's series given by

$$e^{2h} = 1 + 2h + (2h)^2 + (2h)^3 + (2h)^4 + \dots \quad (5)$$

$$3! - 4!$$

(7)

Under the local assumptions, the terms up to h^3 have been cancelled, then Equation 7 becomes:

$$LTE(TOOSS) = \frac{1}{24} h^4 \left[f^{(3)}(x_n, y(x_n)) - f^{(2)}(x_n, y(x_n)) \right] + O(h^5) \quad (8)$$

(8)

Hence, the TOOSS has the convergence of third order.

Order of convergence of SOOSS

The Taylor's series expression for $y(x)$ in powers of h is given by:

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{LTE(TOOSS)}{h^2} = O(h^2) \quad (14)$$

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{LTE(SOOSS)}{h^2} = O(h^2)$$

□

□ □

□ □

From Equation 14, it is observed that TOOSS has consistency characteristics.

Consistency analysis of SOOSS

Following the same procedures as that of the Qureshi and Fadugba (2018), one obtains that:

$$\frac{LTE(SOOSS)}{h^2} = O(h^2) \quad (15)$$

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{LTE(SOOSS)}{h^2} = O(h^2)$$

□ □

From Equation 15, it is observed that SOOSS has consistency characteristics.

Remark

For a numerical technique to be consistent, it is important Fadugba 3 for the truncation errors to be zero when the step size h gets smaller and ultimately reaches to zero.

STABILITY ANALYSES OF THE SCHEMES

A numerical integration method is said to be stable if it is capable of damping out the small fluctuations carried out in the input data. A one step explicit numerical integration method is reserved to be stable if a small perturbation in the initial conditions of the IVP leads to a small perturbation in the following numerical approximation.

Stability analysis of TOOSS

For the stability analysis of TOOSS, one of the popular ways is to apply the scheme to the Dahlquist’s test equation:

$$y'(x) = -y(x), y(0) = 1 \quad (16)$$

0

whose exact solution is given

by

$$y(x) = \exp(-x) \quad (17)$$

where α is, in general, a constant. For an integration interval $[x_n, x_{n+1}]$, where

$$h = x_{n+1} - x_n \quad (18)$$

The exact solution at the point

$$x = x_{n+1}$$

is obtained as (19)

$$y(x_{n+1}) = \exp(-x_{n+1}) = y(x_n) \exp(-h) \quad (20)$$

The numerical approximation obtained using TOOSS gives

$$y_n \approx 1 + \frac{1}{2!} h^2 y'' + \frac{1}{3!} h^3 y''' + \dots \quad (21)$$

Setting

$$A \approx 1 + \frac{1}{2!} h^2 + \frac{1}{3!} h^3 \quad (22)$$

2! 3!

Equation 21 becomes

$$y_n \approx A y_n \quad (23) \quad \text{Afr. J. Math. Comput. Sci. Res.}$$

Figure 1. The stability region (unshaded) of TOOSS.

Comparison of Equations 20 and 23 shows that the factor A is merely an approximation for the factor $\exp(h)$ in the exact solution. Truly, the factor A is the four-term approximation for the Maclaurin's series for $\exp(h)$ for small h . The error growth factor A can be controlled by $A \approx 1$ so that the errors may not magnify. Thus, the stability of TOOSS requires that

$$\|z\| \leq A \approx 1, \quad |z| \leq h \quad (24)$$

Using Equation 24, the stability region is plotted in Figure 1. Hence, TOOSS is found to be stable in Figure 1.

Stability analysis of SOOSS

To discuss the stability analysis of SOOSS, consider the following Dahlquist's test equation of the form:

$$y'(x) = -\lambda y(x), \quad y(0) = 1, \quad \lambda > 0 \quad (25)$$

The exact solution of Equation 25 is given by

$$y(x) = \exp(-x) \tag{26}$$

For an integration interval $[x_n, x_{n+1}]$, where $h = x_{n+1} - x_n$ and following the procedures of Qureshi and Fadugba

(2018); the exact solution at the point $x = x_{n+1}$ is obtained as:

$$y(x_{n+1}) = y(x_n) \exp(-h) \tag{27}$$

When applied SOOSS on this test problem, one gets:

$$y_{n+1} = B y_n \tag{28}$$

where

$$B = 1 - \frac{h^2}{2!} \tag{29}$$

Comparing Equations 27 and 28, it is clearly seen that

Equation 28 is a three-term approximation for the function e^{-h} in the exact solution. The error growth factor given by Equation 28 can be controlled by $B = 1 - \frac{h^2}{2!}$ so that the errors may not amplify. Thus, the stability function of SOOSS requires that:

$$\left\| \frac{1 - \frac{z^2}{2!}}{1 - z} \right\| < 1 \tag{30}$$

Setting

$$z = \lambda h \tag{31}$$

Therefore, Equation 30 becomes:

$$\left\| \frac{1 - \frac{z^2}{2!}}{1 - z} \right\| < 1 \tag{32}$$

The region of absolute stability for SOOSS is defined by the region in the complex plane such

$$\left\| \frac{1 - \frac{z^2}{2!}}{1 - z} \right\| < 1$$

Figure 2.

Remark

The notion of stability may be taken in different contexts: it may be associated with the specific numerical technique used, or the step size h used in numerical computations or with the particular problem being solved.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES AND DISCUSSION

Here presents the implementation of the two schemes on IVPs of stiff differential equations. The discussion of

Figure 2. The stability region (unshaded) of SOOSS.

results is also presented. All the calculations were carried out via MATLAB R2014a, Version: 8.3.0.552, 32 bit (win 32) in double precision.

Example 1

$$y'' = 100(y - x) - 1, y(0) = 1, x \in [0, 0.1], y(x) = \exp(-100x) - x$$

Example 2

$$y'' = 20y - 24, y(0) = 0, x \in [0, 0.1], y(x) = \frac{6}{5} (1 - \exp(-20x))$$

Example 3

$$y'' = 10(y - x)^2, y(0) = 2, x \in [0, 0.1], y(x) = 1 + \frac{1}{10x + 1}$$

The final absolute relative errors at $x = b$ defined by

$$FABRE = \frac{\|y(b) - y_N\|}{\|y_N\|}$$

generated via SOOSS and

TOOSS for Examples 1 to 3 are shown in Tables 1 to 3, respectively. The plots of the Tables 1 to 3 were displayed in Figures 3 to 5, respectively.

It is observed from Tables 1 to 3 that both SOOSS and TOOSS perform excellently and yield smaller error for every decreasing step length, h . It is also observed from Tables 1 to 3 that the order of accuracy of SOOSS and TOOSS have been confirmed when applied to stiff differential equations taking the step length h having a first order decrease in its magnitude, that is $h = 10^{-2}, 10^{-3}$, Fadugba 5

Table 1. The FABRE via SOOSS and TOOSS for Example 1.

h	SOOSS	TOOSS
10^{-2}	0.00089917	0.00002888
10^{-3}	0.00000081	0.00000002

10-4	0.00000001	0.00000000
10-5	0.00000000	0.00000000
10-6	0.00000000	0.00000000

Table 2. The FABRE via SOOSS and TOOSS for Example 2.

<i>h</i>	SOOSS	TOOSS
10-2	0.00240159	0.00014029
10-3	0.00002088	0.00000012
10-4	0.00000021	0.00000000
10-5	0.00000000	0.00000000
10-6	0.00000000	0.00000000

Table 3. The FABRE via SOOSS and TOOSS for Example 3.

h	SOOSS	TOOSS
10-2	0.00139160	0.00012157
10-3	0.00001210	0.00000010
10-4	0.00000012	0.00000000
10-5	0.00000000	0.00000000
10-6	0.00000000	0.00000000

10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} . It is clearly seen in Tables 1 to 3 for every decrease in h , there are second order and third-order decrease in the magnitude of the computed FABRE via SOOSS and TOOSS, respectively. It is observed from the Figures 3 to 5 that the FABREs generated via SOOSS are greater than that of the TOOSS.

Conclusion

In this paper, notes on the order of convergence, consistency and stability properties of TOOSS and SOOSS have been successfully presented. It is observed that TOOSS and SOOSS have the convergence of third order and second order, respectively. From the analysis, it is observed that the two methods are convergent, consistent since they have order of accuracy greater than 1. It is also observed that TOOSS and SOOSS are stable as shown in Figures 1 and 2, respectively. Hence, it can be concluded from the numerical results that TOOSS performs better than SOOSS since it has a higher order of accuracy.

Figure 3. The plot of the FABRE generated via SOOSS and TOOSS using Table 1.

Figure 4. The plot of the FABRE generated via SOOSS and TOOSS using Table 2.

Figure 5. The plot of the FABRE generated via SOOSS and TOOSS using Table 3.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The author has not declared any conflict of interests.

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